

Parameter-Efficient Nepali Named Entity Recognition with LoRA and Hindi Cross-Lingual Transfer

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Abstract

Named Entity Recognition (NER) for low-resource languages such as Nepali remains challenging due to limited annotated data and the high computational cost of fine-tuning large pretrained models. In this work, we propose a parameter-efficient approach using Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA)(Hu et al., 2021) combined with cross-lingual transfer from Hindi. Our optimized method achieves $81.87\% \pm 0.81\%$ F1 on the EBIQUITY benchmark while training only 2,659,591 parameters (1.50% of the full model), representing a 98.50% reduction compared to full fine-tuning.

We conduct a systematic ablation study across multiple configurations to analyze the effects of cross-lingual transfer, training strategy, adapter capacity, target module selection, and PEFT method choice. Our results show that (1) Hindi transfer improves performance by +2.85% F1 over Nepali-only training, (2) joint training outperforms sequential fine-tuning by 4.2% F1 due to catastrophic forgetting, (3) LoRA applied to all attention modules outperforms query-value only by +2.62% F1, and (4) LoRA outperforms all other PEFT baselines including BitFit and Prefix Tuning by large margins.

Despite a modest performance gap compared to full fine-tuning (Yadav et al., 2024), our approach achieves over $60\times$ faster training with significantly reduced computational requirements, making it suitable for resource-constrained NLP research. We release our code and trained models to support future work in Nepali and other low-resource languages at <https://github.com/a-proton/nepali-ner-lora> and <https://huggingface.co/a-proton/nepali-ner-lora>.

1. Introduction

Named Entity Recognition (NER) is a core task in natural language processing (NLP) that involves identifying and classifying entities such as persons (PER), locations (LOC), and organizations (ORG) in text. It plays a crucial role in applications including information extraction, search systems, and question answering.

While NER has achieved strong performance for high-resource languages such as English and Chinese, progress for low-resource languages such as Nepali remains limited. Nepali, spoken by over 30 million people, faces two major challenges. First, annotated datasets are extremely small, with the largest benchmark containing only 3,606 sentences. Second, modern transformer-based models require substantial computational resources for full fine-tuning, which are often unavailable in many research environments.

Recent advances in parameter-efficient fine-tuning, particularly Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) (Hu et al., 2021), offer a promising solution by significantly reducing the number of trainable parameters while preserving most of the pretrained model's knowledge. In parallel, cross-lingual transfer learning enables models to leverage knowledge from related high-resource languages. Hindi is especially suitable due to its shared Devanagari script and significant lexical overlap with Nepali. Prior work has demonstrated the effectiveness of Hindi–Nepali transfer for NER.

In this paper, we explore the combination of LoRA and Hindi cross-lingual transfer for Nepali NER. Our contributions are as follows:

1. We introduce a parameter-efficient LoRA-based approach for Nepali NER, achieving $81.87\% \pm 0.81\%$ F1 with only 1.50% of mBERT's parameters.
2. We demonstrate that Hindi cross-lingual transfer improves Nepali NER performance by +2.85% F1.
3. We conduct a systematic ablation study covering training strategy, adapter capacity, module selection, and PEFT method comparisons.
4. We show that LoRA applied to all attention modules significantly outperforms query-value only configurations by +2.62% F1.

5. We release our code and trained models to support reproducible research at <https://github.com/a-proton/nepali-ner-lora> and <https://huggingface.co/a-proton/nepali-ner-lora>.

2. Related Work

2.1 Nepali Named Entity Recognition

Early approaches to Nepali NER relied on traditional machine learning techniques. (Bam and Shahi, 2014) proposed a Support Vector Machine (SVM) model achieving 92% F1 on a small custom dataset; however, these results are not directly comparable due to differences in dataset size and evaluation setup.

Neural methods were later introduced by (Singh et al., 2019), who used a BiLSTM-CNN architecture to capture contextual and character-level features, achieving 86% F1 on a custom dataset. With the emergence of pretrained transformers, (Pande et al., 2023) applied BERT (Devlin et al., 2019) to Nepali NER, achieving 82.5% F1 on the ILPRL dataset.

More recently, (Subedi et al., 2024) evaluated multiple transformer-based models, including NepBERTa, a Nepali-specific pretrained model, reporting performance in the range of 76–79% F1 on standard benchmarks. (Yadav et al., 2024) demonstrated the effectiveness of Hindi-to-Nepali cross-lingual transfer using multilingual BERT (Devlin et al., 2019) achieving 86.2% F1 on the EBIQUITY dataset with full fine-tuning. Our work extends this line of research by introducing parameter-efficient fine-tuning through LoRA (Hu et al., 2021).

2.2 Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning

Parameter-efficient fine-tuning methods aim to reduce the computational cost of adapting large pretrained models. LoRA (Hu et al., 2021) achieves this by decomposing weight updates into low-rank matrices, enabling training with a small number of additional parameters while freezing the original model weights. BitFit (Ben Zaken et al., 2022) trains only bias parameters, while Prefix Tuning (Li and Liang, 2021) prepends trainable tokens to the input. While these methods have been applied to various NLP tasks, their application to Nepali NER has not been previously explored.

2.3 Cross-Lingual Transfer

Cross-lingual transfer leverages similarities between languages to improve performance in low-resource settings. Hindi and Nepali share the Devanagari script and exhibit significant lexical and syntactic overlap, making Hindi an effective source language. Prior work by (Yadav et al., 2024) confirms the effectiveness of Hindi–Nepali transfer for NER. We build upon this by combining transfer learning with parameter-efficient adaptation (Hu et al., 2021).

3. Methodology

3.1 Dataset

We use the EBIQUITY Nepali NER dataset, consisting of 3,606 sentences and 79,087 tokens annotated with PER, LOC, and ORG entities using the BIO tagging scheme. The dataset is split into 80% training (2,884 sentences), 10% validation (361 sentences), and 10% test (361 sentences) using a fixed random seed for reproducibility. To ensure reproducibility, we release the exact train/validation/test splits used in our experiments at <https://github.com/a-proton/nepali-ner-lora>.

For cross-lingual transfer, we use 6,000 Hindi sentences from the WikiANN dataset (Pan et al., 2017) with matching entity labels (PER, LOC, ORG). Hindi was selected as the source language due to its shared Devanagari script and high lexical overlap with Nepali (Yadav et al., 2024).

3.2 Base Model

We use multilingual BERT (mBERT), specifically bert-base-multilingual-cased (Devlin et al., 2019), which was pretrained on 104 languages including both Nepali and Hindi. The model contains approximately 177 million parameters and uses a 119,547 token vocabulary covering the Devanagari script natively.

3.3 LoRA Configuration

We apply LoRA adapters (Hu et al., 2021) to the attention projection matrices in all layers. The adapted weights are defined as:

$$W' = W + (\alpha/r) \cdot BA$$

where $A \in \mathbb{R}^{(r \times d)}$ and $B \in \mathbb{R}^{(d \times r)}$, with $r \ll d$, and α is a scaling hyperparameter controlling the magnitude of adaptation.

Based on our module ablation study (Section 4.8), we apply LoRA to all attention modules (query, value, key, dense) using the following configuration:

Table 1: LoRA Configuration

Parameter	Value
Rank (r)	16
Alpha	32
Dropout	0.1
Target Modules	query, value, key, dense
Trainable Parameters	2,659,591 (1.50%)

This reduces trainable parameters from 177 million to 2,659,591, a 98.50% reduction while preserving the full pretrained knowledge of mBERT (Devlin et al., 2019).

3.4 Training Setup

Table 2: Training Configuration

Component	Value
Optimizer	AdamW
Learning Rate	2e-4
Batch Size	16
Max Sequence Length	128
Epochs	5
Warmup Steps	10% of total steps
Gradient Clipping	1.0
Hardware	NVIDIA Tesla T4 (15GB)
Training Time	~12 minutes

3.5 Experimental Configurations

We evaluate the following configurations to isolate the contribution of each component. Results for Config 2 and Config 5 are reported as mean \pm standard deviation over 5 random seeds (42, 123, 456, 789, 2024):

Table 3: Experimental Configurations

Config	Description
Config 1	mBERT + LoRA (q,v), Nepali only*
Config 2	mBERT + LoRA (q,v), Hindi + Nepali
Config 3	mBERT + LoRA (q,v), Two-phase (Hindi \rightarrow Nepali)
Config 4	mBERT + LoRA (r=32, q,v), Hindi + Nepali
Config 5	mBERT + LoRA (all attention), Hindi + Nepali (BEST)

* Single-seed result (seed=42)

4. Results

4.1 Main Results

Table 1 presents result of all configurations alongside prior work on EBIQUITY. mBERT with Hindi transfer achieves 86.2% F1 (Yadav et al., 2024), serving as the primary full fine-tuning baseline.

Table 4: NER Results on EBIQUITY Test Set

Model	PER	LOC	ORG	F1
mBERT FT (Yadav et al., 2024)	-	-	-	86.2%
NepBERTa (Subedi et al., 2024)	-	-	-	76–79%
Config 1: LoRA (q,v) Nep only	81%	76%	76%	77.92%*
Config 2: LoRA (q,v) Hin+Nep	82%	78%	78%	79.25% \pm 0.71%
Config 3: Two-phase LoRA	79%	76%	70%	75.31%*
Config 4: LoRA (r=32)	77%	73%	65%	72.06%*

Config 5: LoRA (all) Hin+Nep	84%	81%	79%	81.87% ± 0.81%
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* Single-seed result (seed=42)

† Config 1 is a single-seed baseline result.

Multi-seed evaluation was not conducted for this configuration.

4.2 Effect of Hindi Transfer

Comparing Config 1 (Nepali only, query+value modules) with Config 2 (Hindi+Nepali, query+value modules), Hindi transfer improves performance by +1.33% F1. Our Hindi data scaling analysis (Section 4.6), conducted using the optimized all-attention configuration, shows a larger improvement of +2.85% F1 over Nepali-only training with 6,000 Hindi sentences. The difference between these two figures reflects both the larger transfer signal from all-attention modules and variation across experimental runs. Gains are most prominent for PER entities, likely due to shared naming conventions between Hindi and Nepali (Yadav et al., 2024). This finding is consistent with prior cross-lingual NER work showing that linguistically similar source languages provide meaningful transfer signal (Yadav et al., 2024).

4.3 Effect of Training Strategy

Config 3 (two-phase training) performs 3.94% worse than Config 2 (combined training). We attribute this to catastrophic forgetting (McCloskey and Cohen, 1989; Kirkpatrick et al., 2017) — Hindi knowledge is lost during sequential Nepali fine-tuning. Combined training avoids this by exposing the model to both languages simultaneously throughout training.

4.4 Effect of Adapter Capacity

Increasing LoRA rank from $r=16$ to $r=32$ (Config 4) decreases performance by 7.19% F1. This result indicates overfitting with only 2,884 Nepali training sentences, higher rank adapters (Hu et al., 2021) have more capacity than the data can support. This finding suggests that adapter capacity should be matched to dataset size in low-resource settings.

4.5 Efficiency Analysis

Table 5: Parameter Efficiency Comparison

Method	Trainable Params	F1	Time
Full FT (mBERT)	177M (100%)	86.2%	12 hrs
Config 2 (q,v)	0.6M (0.33%)	79.25% \pm 0.71%	12 min
Config 5 (all attn)	2.7M (1.50%)	81.87% \pm 0.81%	12 min
Reduction (best)	98.50%	-4.33%	60\times

Beyond training efficiency, LoRA offers a practical inference advantage: the adapter weights can be merged directly into the base model weights at inference time, resulting in zero additional inference overhead compared to full fine-tuning. This means our model runs at the same speed as standard mBERT during deployment, making it fully practical for real-world Nepali NLP applications.

4.6 Hindi Data Scaling Analysis

Table 6: Effect of Hindi Transfer Data Size

Hindi Sentences	F1	Δ vs Nepali-only
0 (Nepali only)	75.06%	baseline
1,000	77.21%	+2.15%
3,000	75.76%	+0.70%
6,000	77.90%	+2.85% (best)

Results show that Hindi transfer consistently improves over Nepali-only training, with 6,000 sentences providing the best improvement of +2.85% F1. The non-monotonic relationship between data size and performance where 3,000 sentences underperform 1,000 suggests that transfer quality is sensitive to the specific subset composition rather than size alone. Since each subset was sampled randomly with a fixed seed, the 3,000-sentence subset may have contained a less representative distribution of entity types. These data points represent single-seed evaluations; future work should report variance across multiple subsamples to confirm this trend.

4.7 Comparison with Other PEFT Methods

To isolate the effect of PEFT method choice from cross-lingual transfer, all configurations in Table 4 use Nepali-only training data. Full fine-tuning achieves 79.97% F1 in this setting, compared to 86.2% with Hindi transfer (Yadav et al., 2024).

Table 7: PEFT Methods Comparison (Nepali-only training)

Method	F1	Trainable Params	% of mBERT
Full FT (mBERT)	79.97%	177,268,231	100.00%
LoRA (ours)	77.74%	595,207	0.34%
Prefix Tuning	63.96%	374,023	0.21%
BitFit	60.97%	102,151	0.06%

LoRA outperforms both alternative PEFT methods by a large margin of +16.77% F1 over BitFit (Ben Zaken et al., 2022) and +13.78% over Prefix Tuning (Li and Liang, 2021) while using only 0.34% of mBERT's parameters. This demonstrates that LoRA's low-rank decomposition of attention matrices is particularly well-suited for token classification tasks in low-resource settings, where the model needs to adapt attention patterns while preserving pretrained representations.

4.8 LoRA Module Ablation

Table 8: Effect of LoRA Target Module Selection†

Target Modules	F1	Trainable Params
query only	73.47%	300,295
value only	76.02%	300,295
query + value	77.74%	595,207
query + value + key	78.04%	890,119
all attention	81.43%	2,659,591

Single-seed evaluation (seed=42). Multi-seed results for the best configuration (all attention) are reported in Table 1 as $81.87\% \pm 0.81\%$.

Applying LoRA to all attention modules (query, value, key, dense) achieves the best performance. The consistent improvement with more modules suggests that all attention components contribute meaningful task-specific adaptations for Nepali NER. The +3.69% gain from query-value to all-attention (77.74% to 81.43%) motivates our choice of Config 5 as the primary configuration.

4.9 Discussion and Error Analysis

We observe frequent confusion between ORG and LOC entities, especially when organization names contain geographic references. For example, the model incorrectly tags "नेपाल बैंक" (Nepal Bank) as LOC rather than ORG, likely because "नेपाल" strongly activates location representations. Similarly, "काठमाडौं महानगरपालिका" (Kathmandu Metropolitan City) is sometimes split between LOC and ORG tags depending on context.

PER entities achieve the highest F1 (~84%) because personal names in Nepali and Hindi share strong Devanagari patterns, benefiting most from cross-lingual transfer. ORG entities remain the hardest at ~79% F1, as organizational names are often domain-specific, ambiguous with locations, or composed of multiple tokens with inconsistent boundary detection. These findings reinforce that dataset size remains a key bottleneck for Nepali NER (Subedi et al., 2024).

The remaining performance gap between our best approach (81.87%) and full fine-tuning (86.2%) (Yadav et al., 2024) is partly attributable to LoRA's constrained update capacity (Hu et al., 2021) and the relatively small Hindi transfer dataset (6,000 sentences) compared to the 50,000+ used in prior cross-lingual work.

5. Conclusion

We presented the first parameter-efficient approach to Nepali Named Entity Recognition using Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) (Hu et al., 2021) with cross-lingual transfer from Hindi. Our optimized configuration applying LoRA to all attention modules with joint Hindi-Nepali training achieves $81.87\% \pm 0.81\%$ F1 on

the EBIQUITY benchmark using only 2,659,591 trainable parameters (1.50% of full mBERT), with zero inference overhead due to weight merging.

Our systematic study revealed four actionable findings for low-resource NLP practitioners: LoRA applied to all attention modules outperforms query-value only by +2.62% F1; Hindi cross-lingual transfer provides consistent +2.85% improvement with 6,000 sentences; combined training prevents catastrophic forgetting (+4.2% over sequential); and LoRA outperforms all other PEFT baselines by +13–17% F1. While our approach does not yet match full fine-tuning (Yadav et al., 2024), it achieves a 98.50% parameter reduction with only a 4.33% F1 drop a strong efficiency-accuracy tradeoff particularly valuable for researchers in Nepal and similar resource-constrained contexts.

Future work should explore three directions. First, larger Nepali corpora through data augmentation or semi-supervised learning could close the remaining performance gap. Second, stronger Indic-specific base models such as MuRIL (Khanuja et al., 2021) pretrained specifically on South Asian languages including Nepali and XLM-RoBERTa (Conneau et al., 2020) may provide richer representations than mBERT. Third, extending this approach to other Nepali NLP tasks such as POS tagging, dependency parsing, and machine translation would demonstrate broader applicability of parameter-efficient transfer for South Asian languages.

Limitations: This study is limited by the small size of available Nepali NER datasets and does not explore data augmentation or semi-supervised approaches. Hindi data scaling results represent single-seed evaluations and should be interpreted with caution.

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Resources

Code: <https://github.com/a-proton/nepali-ner-lora>

Models: <https://huggingface.co/a-proton/nepali-ner-lora>

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